
An Urban Park Retrofit: Integrating the “ Young Millennials ” Perception of Space in Malcolm Square, Baguio City

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Abstract: This study explores the spatial preferences of young millennials in Malcolm Square, Baguio City, to create an urban park design suitable for their unique social and recreational behaviors. Known for their affinity for technology and social interaction, Baguio City millennials represent a significant portion of the population in public places yet often use their mobile devices in parks, limiting their engagement in the public realm. The study uses observational data, behavioral mapping, and survey questionnaires to determine what factors attract these demographics to Malcolm Square and their activities. Findings show that millennials are motivated by social and recreational opportunities. Yet, much of their park engagement is private and digital, revealing a disconnect between intended park functions and current use. The study addresses how millennials' spatial perceptions manifest in their public behaviors, influenced by urban dynamics, safety, and comfort. This research contributes to understanding how generational preferences impact urban park design, promoting a model that harmonizes with evolving generational needs and reinforces community bonds in Baguio City's urban parks.

Keywords: Urban Park, Malcolm Square, Young Millennials, Retrofit, Perception, Urban Dynamics

Introduction

The rapid population growth in the 2000s urges solutions to urban cities to provide an adequate level of experience of relaxation and recreation. Moreover, the improvement of these urban territories must be trailed to provide space for respite, idealism, training/education, and social collaboration for the millennial ages. (Angkasa, Z. 2019) The Millennial Generation, categorically tagged as: “Generation Y”, the “Me Generation”, “Selfie Generation” or the “Digital Natives” born between 1981 to 2000 is bound to make a significant impact. They are the new generation of young adults that comprise the majority of the Philippine population. In Baguio City, they are the largest age group making up 22 % of the household population in 2015. (POPCEN 2015) Today in their 20s and 30s, they are projected to be the world's most essential and influential generational cohort to global economic and business opportunities. There has been a particular distinction between this age group from its precursors. The qualities and propensities they have affect what they value in terms of the environment and experiences. Socialization and the inclination toward advanced

technologies are the common denominators of this group. Amid rapid urban development and the increasing use of technology and social media, there will be a time when they need public space to interact and socialize. Malcolm Square, also known as “People’s Park”, is one of the historical landmarks of the famed “Summer Capital of the Philippines”: Baguio City. The city seldom sleeps with activities happening from dawn to dusk. The city is community-driven and with the rehabilitation of Malcolm Square in 2018, it made its mark as a significant step in the primacy of public spaces. It has been transformed into an open space that welcomes residents and tourists regardless of demographics, a breathing space from the hustle of Magsaysay Avenue and Session Road. Young millennials also frequent this place; however, one common scenario suggests that their private engagement using mobile phones leads to their withdrawal from public life. Technologies such as the mobile phone may further undermine their public life by increasing the opportunity for them to spend time in private while in public spaces. Their affinity with the digital world sets them apart. Integrating their preferences in common public and green spaces in urban areas helps enliven these urban areas. Studies have shown that younger millennials are more interested in the social aspect of outdoor recreation compared to passive recreational activities. (Mowen et.al 2007, Skinner, Sarpong & White 2018 as cited by Melhalf,2019) The accessible City Parks can be optimized for attracting the millennial generation by understanding the factors that attract visits to city parks. However, research aiming to understand the attractive factors of millennial visits is still trivial. (Angkasa. Z. 2019) The challenge is: how would these digital natives unplug and get into the park?

Research Problem and Problem Setting

Research Problem

“Space is not a silent void. Space speaks. Its language is a movement” (McMillan, J. 2020). Spatial dynamics is the study and enhancement of the relationship between humans and space. It also increases the connection to the personal space and the space that is shared with others. This study will be one of the first attempts to evaluate the current philosophies in designing urban parks to include the preferences of young millennials. It sought to study the correlation between social recreation or activities that enhance the social skills that allow participants to build life-long friendships in real-life situations; activities that people take part with others (Bell Socialization 2020) and the young millennials' spatial perception or the ability to perceive spatial relationships in respect to the orientation of one's body despite distracting information (Donnon, T; DesCôteaux, JG & Violato, C. (2005). Spatial perception is usually understood as the “space” around us, objects, elements, and the part of our thinking as it is where we put all our lived experiences together. Moreover, to analyze their activities, behaviors, and characteristics that will contribute to the understanding of spatial dynamics suited to them as well. These will be considered as pull factors used to attract more of them to the park. Consequently, the research would aim to answer the following questions: How does the young Millennials' spatial perception manifest in various forms of social recreation in Malcolm Square?

1. What are the existing features of Malcolm Square?
2. How do these existing features contribute to millennials' activities in the square?
3. How do the young millennials define social recreation in Malcolm Square?
4. Is their perception of social recreation seen in the current design of Malcolm Square?
5. Is the intended use of Malcolm Square consistent with its actual use?

Research Objectives

With the absorption of technology in their daily lives, the trend of co-working & co-living communities, the age of digital friends, and structured co-living environments, the millennial generation is bound to influence the design of urban parks. The objectives of the study are the following:

1. To identify the existing features of Malcolm Square that attract young millennials.
2. To determine the different activities of these demographics in Malcolm Square and incorporate them into the design of Malcolm Square.
3. To identify the different forms of social-recreational activities in Malcolm Square and generate concepts that will attract more young millennials to visit the park.
4. To identify their distinct behaviors in the use of the park which will encourage liveliness while being consistent with their perception of social recreation.
5. To evaluate the current use of Malcolm Square in comparison to its intended use.

Description of the Case Study

The research study will be focused on the Young Millennials of Baguio City ages 20 to 28 years old mostly college students and young working and non-working age groups regardless of gender and ethnicity, the locality evolves in Malcolm Square, Baguio City, popularly known as “People’s Park”. This is edified by the bust of George Malcolm who is figuratively referred to as the “Father of Baguio City”, who spearheaded the creation of the City’s Charter (Murillo,2013). The park is a public space nestled at the heart of the city, located at the foot of the renowned Session Road, and considered as Kilometer Zero (See Figure 1).

Significance of the Study

Nowadays, people are most likely to spend more time alone, in their private spaces, limited only to virtual social interactions due to the Internet, smartphones, and other technological advancements disconnecting people from physical contact and social interaction. There is a dearth of knowledge on how to motivate effectively specific demographics towards recreational pursuits. There is a call for planners to update design concepts and philosophies, taking into consideration the characteristics and the ever-evolving needs of the millennials. The research could provide information on the issues related to the creation of urban parks suited for the growing number of millennials which blends with the needs of the other generation as well. The findings of this study will redound to the benefit of society and other cities. The research will uncover not only the characteristics, traits, and behaviors in the usage of urban parks, of the booming "Generation Y" but to integrate it into the creation of a distinct venue for them as well as capitalize on this to promote the socio-cultural and economic growth of the city. Further, the integration of their perception of space will create a vibrant urban park that will not only cater to this particular demographic but all generations. For the researcher, the study would help in discovering gaps in the field of urban design; thus, a new theory on designing communal spaces for distinct millennials may be derived.

Review of Literature

How is the Millennial Generation Reshaping Cities and Urban Tourism?-Ruspini, E. & Marxiano M. (2016) emphasized the growing importance of the millennials and their peculiar practices, behavior, and lifestyle explores particular environments that depict innovation, creativity, and multi-sensorial experiences mixing virtual, social aspects and technology. The needs of the generation have profoundly transformed

and are still translating into our cities. Age demographics contribute to the success of a plan or redevelopment. It is high time to begin building environments and communities that consider a younger stakeholder.

The components of the public sphere in the context of mass media, civic institutions, and informal civic actions are conceptualized as an opportunity for the exchange of messages with several others in public spaces (Hampton, Goulet, & Albanesius, 2015). This context of public space has changed over the years with the emergence of advanced technologies that make people alone in public spaces. Several studies in the USA have found that people are increasingly likely to live alone, engage with smaller social circles, disengage from civic institutions, and spend time in private spaces (Hampton et al., 2011c; Klinenberg, 2012; Lofland, 1998; Putnam, 2000). However, the assumption of these shifts generally has effects on engagement in public spaces. The opportunities for private engagement led to a withdrawal from public life (Sennett, 1977). The mobile phone is one technology that may further undermine public life by increasing the opportunity for people to spend time in private while in public spaces (Turkle, 2011). The list of social changes that may have affected public interactions over a period that coincides with the rise of new digital technologies is long and includes trends that urban Literature has treated extensively. (Hampton et al., 2015) In the context of designing public spaces such as city parks in the current era, a large number of the end-users catered to by these facilities are the millennials otherwise called: Generation Y, Digital Natives, or The Selfie Generation. Millennials, the group of people born between the mid-1980s and early 2000s, are different from their Generation X counterparts in many ways. They

Figure 1: *Malcolm Square Site*. (n.d.). [Photograph]. Google Maps Malcolm Square.
<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Malcolm+Square>

are tech-savvy, socially conscious, achievement-driven people with more flexible ideas about wealth, work, and play. (Hornick, 2015). With the rapid advancement of technology and issues brought about by it discussed above. A primary recipient of these advantages and disadvantages of modernization is the millennials. Millennials are digital natives, and because of social media and access to the internet are not

used to feeling alone. Given the social nature of these individuals, parks, and recreation areas that offer a chance for group activities are more likely to appeal to them. Not only are Millennials used to having ready access to the internet via smartphones and tablets, but they also use these devices to share their travel and recreation experiences in real time. Consequently, these also serve as barriers for them to visit the park. In designing urban parks, it is vital to understand the immediate concerns and requirements of the majority of its users, and in the case of this study will be catered to the young millennials. The Millennials want to live in places that share a lot of the same characteristics as urban centers—they are looking for amenities like walkability and public transit. Thanks to the generation's size and influence, millennials are moving to new places made just for them, by them—revitalizing smaller cities or opting for hybridized urban-burb enclaves where the quality of life is the driving force. (Walker, 2016) To make an underperforming space into a vital "place," physical elements must be introduced that would make people welcome and comfortable, such as seating and new landscaping, and also through "management" changes in the pedestrian circulation pattern. Moreover, this is also achieved by developing more productive relationships between the surrounding retail and the activities going on in the public spaces. The goal is to create a place that has both a strong sense of community and a comfortable image. (PPS, 2015)

Theoretical Framework

Urban spaces are important places where people can convene, thus they create an atmosphere and the identity of the community. The proposal draws inspiration from different theories on urban design. The ideas will serve as fundamental tools in guiding the conduct of this research. These were uncovered in two folds firstly, Kevin Lynch's "Theory of Good City Forms" emphasizes the union of the quality of space and human activity characterized by identity, structure, congruence, and legibility. The theory serves as a guide in the place-making for young millennials considering the following:

- a. Convenience and safe access to and through the park.
- b. Attractive and Vibrant Urban Parks,
- c. Support Activity, Safety, and Amenities, and,
- d. Comfortability and entertainment.

The Gestalt laws of a perceptual organization determined the young millennials' distinct behavior and characteristics in the usage of the space. These identified young Millennial's spatial perception that manifests in various forms of social recreation in Malcolm Square. It aided in creating a distinct environment characterized by innovation, creativity, multi-sensorial experiences mixing virtual and social aspects, and smart, and social mobile technology catering to all users regardless of age demographics.

Methodology

The study is descriptive and focused on young millennials ages 20 to 28 years old regardless of gender, culture, and ethnicity. The researcher used historical, descriptive methodologies, and investigative studies. The historical method aided the researcher in understanding the history and evolution of Malcolm Square to have a clear understanding of its usage in the historical context. The method was used to gather data about the activities and behaviors of the young millennials in Malcolm Square. These contributed to the understanding of the young millennials' spatial perception that manifests in various forms of social recreation in Malcolm Square. On the other hand, the investigative study intended to seek the characteristics of the young millennials and the logic of why they should be incorporated into the design of the city park. The instruments used in the study involved survey questionnaires, interviews, behavioral mapping,

photo-documentation, and site visitations. These were supported by related literature, journals, similar case studies, and research studies.

A. Survey Respondents and Coverage- A questionnaire was an essential tool in gathering relevant information from the respondents. The data-gathering method was designed to contain a concise, structured set of questions to yield specific information related to the activities and behaviors of the millennials that contribute to the understanding of spatial dynamics.

In addition to this, the questionnaires are a pragmatic approach that assessed their views and the relative importance of each environmental and physical attribute. Furthermore, questions raised will seek the ideas of the respondents on how to improve the area.

B. Behavioral mapping was used to record the activities on a map to understand the behavior of the young millennials through the activities concerning the existing buildings adjacent to the spaces within Malcolm Square.

C. Photo documentation was used to document or record the existing features of Malcolm Square.

D. Related Literature, journals, similar case studies, and research studies. This evaluative report of scholarly studies related to the research gave validation, justification, and theoretical basis. The report was limited to the works that were essential and are closely related to the topic area. Moreover, this enabled the researcher to learn from the previous theory. The constructed model revealed the correlation between the millennials and the built environment that promotes culture, creativity, and innovation. Similar case studies gave a basis for the conclusion and recommendation of the project. As such, they served as a guide in conceptualizing the proposed study.

Results and Discussions

History of Malcolm Square

Historically, Malcolm Squares was once utilized by the Ibaloi tribe and other ethnicities as an area of trading and gathering before the arrival of the Americans in Baguio City (Cadalig,2017). In terms of function, Peoples Park can be compared to the Hispanic Plazas “Intramuros” or “Leyes Delos Indio’s” inspired cities and towns in the Philippines. Its ultimate function had been “social “in contextual delineation as it used to be a venue for public announcements of election results and policies of the city and sometimes functioned as a parking lot. Figure 2 shows a view of Malcolm Square in 1960 taken from what was known as Baguio Plaza. From a plain open space flanked with plant boxes and foliage, in the 1990s, the local government transformed the park into an open space that welcomes citizens and visitors alike and is now an apt breathing space from the hustle of Magsaysay Avenue and Session Road (Mata, 2018). Figure 3 shows the current Malcolm Square taken from a vantage point of an overpass located along Magsaysay Avenue. Figure 4 shows the existing condition and features of Malcolm Square.

Figure 2: Baguio Heritage Foundation. (n.d).
Square 1960 [Photograph].
In *Baguio City Plaza*.

Figure 3: Igorot land (n.d). Malcolm Square Malcolm
In *Malcolm Square*.
<https://www.esquiremag.ph>

Figure 4 : Florendo, I. (2020). Malcolm Square
Square Covid Days 2020.

Figure 5: Alinio, V. (2019). Malcolm Square
In *Malcolm Square 2019*.

Survey Respondents and Coverage

A survey was completed to come up with the Urban Park Retrofit of Malcolm Square, Baguio City that will integrate the “Young Millennials” Perception of Space. An arbitrary scale was used to interpret the level of agreement of the respondents. The column scale, weighted average, and qualitative value are as follows: 4=3.26- 4.00 Strongly Agree, 3 = 2.51-3.25, Agree; 2=1.76-2.50 Disagree, and 1=1.00-1.75 Strongly Disagree. The numerical equivalent to measuring comfortability is as follows:

3.26-4.00=Very Comfortable, 2.51-3.25=Comfortable, 1.76-2.50=Fairly Comfortable, and 1.00-1.75= Not Comfortable. The chosen age profile of the respondents considered as “Young Millennials” are ages 20 to 28 years old. Of the 108 respondents, most of those who participated were young adults ages 20 to 22 years old (58.3%), 23 to 25 years old (27.8%), and 26 to 28 years old (11.2%). Most are single (103), 96.4%, and (5) 4.6% are married. (58) 54.2% of the respondents are female, (47) 43.9% are male, and (2) 1.9% prefer not to say. The profile of the respondents as to their category shows that most of those who participated are students (84) 77.8%. Tourists (4) comprise 3.7% of the sample group, while Technical/ Professionals (5) make up 4.6% of it.

As to the profile of the respondents which relates to the number of years of their stay in Baguio City, it was found that most of them have stayed in the city for more than 15 years (40) 37%. Respondents who have resided for 2 to 5 years (34) 31.5%, and 5 to 10 years (19) 17.6%. These respondents can contribute to the realization of the transformation of Malcolm Square that will incorporate their needs without compromising the demands of the other generations. Since they already considered Baguio City as their home, an emotional bond to the place is already deep-rooted therefore they will find means to protect and preserve it as well. Their familiarity with the area also created the “Sense of Place.”Tiong San Bazaar, Tesmelitas (former U-Need), Abellera building, BPI Family Bank, Plaza Theatre building, and PS Bank building are the buildings that are adjacent to the park and are considered built heritage and of historical importance.

The existing features of Malcolm Square attract young millennials

Table 01 shows the existing features of Malcolm Square that attract young millennials. Generally, the respondents strongly agreed on the presence of old/historical buildings that provide a “Sense of place” (provides meaning to the location) (3.32). The general result signifies that the buildings, roadways, sidewalks, pedestrian lanes, and landscapes play a very significant role in the attractiveness and vibrancy of the park thus these factors contribute to the existing features of Malcolm Square that attract the young millennials.

Table 01: The Existing Features of Malcolm Square

	*W.A.	*Q.V.
I. Attractiveness and Vibrant Urban Park		
A.1 Building		
1. Colors of the buildings adjacent to the park characterized by different colors create an appealing environment.	2.47	Agree
2. Presence of old/historical buildings provides a “Sense of place” (provides meaning to the location)	3.32	Strongly Agree
A.2 Roadways/Sidewalks/Pedestrian Lanes		
1. The material of the pavement surface is attractive and comfortable to walk through	2.78	Agree
2. Pedestrian lanes/Crosswalks are strategically located for ease and safe pedestrian access.	2.58	Agree
B.1 Street Furniture/Landscaping		
1. Scenic trees and landscaping elements	2.91	Agree
2. The design of the street furniture blends with the character/design of the environment.	2.74	Agree
3. The walkable environment is amusing, festive, cordial, and sociable. (convivial)	2.99	Agree

II. Convenience and Safety Access		
1. The extent of walking along Lower Session Rd. to Malcolm Square is time-saving and conducive.	3.06	Agree
2. Streets leading to the park can be crossed easily, safely, and without delay.	2.88	Agree
3. The park is interesting, clean, and free from threats.	2.74	Agree
4. Support Activity and Amenities The park is sign posted (eq. walkway lanes/sitting areas)	2.78	Agree
5. There are visible signs for PWD access.	2.55	Agree
III. Comfortability and Entertainment:		
1. The park environment is enjoyable and secure.	2.70	Agree
2. The design of the facilities meets the design standards for sidewalk widths, seating areas, and walking surfaces for all types of pedestrians including the physically challenged pedestrians.	2.79	Agree
Gross Weighted Average (GWA)	2.80	Agree

Numerical Equivalent: 3.26-4.00=Strongly Agree, 2.51-3.25=Agree, 1.76-2.50=Disagree, 1.00-1.75= Strongly Disagree *W. A- Weighted Average, Q.V- Qualitative Value

Perception & Level of Comfort on the Existing Conditions of Malcolm Square

Table 02. Shows how frequently the young millennials visit Malcolm Square, and it was found that they sometimes visit Malcolm Square (63%). The results mean that the park located at the business hub of Baguio City is not always or only visited on some occasions by these demographics.

Table 02. Frequency of Visiting Malcolm Square

	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Never	2	1.9
Sometimes	68	63
Often	29	26.9
Very Often	9	8.2
Total	108	100

Table 03. Shows the purposes of the respondents in visiting Malcolm Square. The majority of them visit Malcolm Square because it is publicly accessible (80.6%). Most of the respondents admitted that they visit the park because it is where they meet people (84.3%) and a convenient place to use a cell phone, text, and social media (40.7%). The results simply imply that Malcolm Square is considered a hub where these demographics can socialize. However, the use of their mobile phones in public places could undermine their public life since they spend their time in private while in public places.

Table 03. Reasons for Visiting Malcolm Square

PURPOSE	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Natural Beauty and Greenery	17	15.7
Reduce Stress & Feel Better/Relaxation	34	31.5
Strengthen Relationships & Bonding	8	7.4
Variety of Physical Activities	20	18.5
Meeting People	91	84.3
Favorite Place	1	.90
Publicly Accessible	87	80.6
A place to be alone in a public place	15	13.9
A good place to take pictures/selfies	7	6.5
A convenient place to use cellphone/texting/social media	44	40.7

Table 04, shows the level of comfort in the existing conditions of Malcolm Square. Generally, the respondents agreed to some extent that they are “Fairly Comfortable” (2.42) with the current condition of the park. Specifically, among the statements provided, the respondents are only comfortable with the volume of people in the park (2.68) and are "fairly comfortable" with the sight of ambulant vendors (2.24) and the sight of people sitting, texting, and doing selfies (2.46). They are also "fairly comfortable" with thermal comfort considering the climate and temperature in the park (2.46) the results convey that the current physical condition of the park seen in the lack of shades can contribute to this feeling. However, they are comfortable (2.57) with walking & visiting the park alone. It connotes that safety and security within the park are highly regarded. Furthermore, they are "fairly comfortable" with hearing acoustics from the establishments (2.17) and music within the park (2.43), as well as being "fairly comfortable" with the smell of air within the park (2.11). Overall, they are comfortable with their ease of movement (2.54) in the park but "fairly comfortable" with the ambiance (2.50). It equates to the general impression of the park visit as "fairly comfortable", (2.48). Findings show that their perception and level of comfort with the existing conditions of Malcolm Square suggest a park retrofit to encourage more young millennials to visit the park.

Table 04. Level of comfort with the existing conditions of Malcolm Square

	*W.A.	*Q.V.
1. Sight How comfortable are you with the volume of People in the park?	2.68	Comfortable
Ambulant sidewalk vendors (How comfortable are you with the number and presence of sidewalk vendors?)	2.24	Fairly Comfortable
How comfortable are you with the sight of people sitting, texting, and doing selfies?	2.46	Fairly Comfortable
2. Thermal Comfort and Feeling How comfortable are you with the Climate/Temperature in the park?	2.46	Fairly Comfortable

Walking & visiting the park alone	2.57	Comfortable
3. Hearing Acoustic Control from the establishments	2.17	Fairly Comfortable
The appropriate type of music within the park	2.43	Fairly Comfortable
4.Smell The air within the park	2.11	Fairly Comfortable
The overall Ease of Movement	2.54	Comfortable
The overall ambiance in Malcolm Square	2.50	Fairly Comfortable
General Impression of the Park Visit	2.48	Fairly Comfortable
Gross Weighted Average (GWA)	2.42	Fairly Comfortable

Numerical Equivalent: 3.26-4.00=Very Comfortable, 2.51-3.25=Comfortable, 1.76-2.50=Fairly Comfortable 1.00-1.75= Not Comfortable *W. A- Weighted Average, Q.V- Qualitative Value

Table 05. What motivates the young millennials to visit the park

	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Attractiveness of the Place	47	43.5
Social and Recreational Activities	85	78.7
Amenities (Free Wi-Fi)	31	28.7
Free Public Toilet	25	23.1

Table 05 shows that these demographics are motivated to visit the park for Social and Recreational Activities present in Malcolm Square (78.7%). The attractiveness of the place (43.5%) also plays a very important role in the motivation of these millennials to visit the park. Amenities (Free Wi-Fi) (28.7%) support their distinct characteristics as “digital natives”.

Social Recreational Activities engaged in Malcolm Square

Table 06. Social Recreational Activities

Activities	Frequency	Percentage
Work with friends/colleagues	29	26.9
Watching Live events/concerts	46	42.6

Physical Fitness/ Dance activities	5	4.8
Reading Textbooks/Papers	4	3.7
Public Arts/Activities	46	42.8
Public Performance and Government Services (Politics)	37	34.3
Mounting cultural festivals/exhibits	24	22.2
People-watching, discussions, and entertainment.	26	24.1
Online games and social media	6	5.6
Picture Taking/Selfies/Groupies	11	10.2
Eating Street Foods/Snacks	30	27.8

Generally, the respondents visit the park to engage in public arts activities (42.8%), watch live events and concerts (42.6%), and for public performances and government activities (34.3%). Specifically, the presence of ambulant vendors and food kiosks near Malcolm Square contributes to making the park a venue for eating street foods and snacks where (27.8%) of the respondents consider this as one of their activities while in Malcolm Square. They also visit the park to work with friends and colleagues (26.9%) and engage in people-watching discussions, and entertainment (24.1%). These results imply how the young millennials define social recreation in Malcolm Square.

Reasons for Engaging in Social Recreational Activities in Malcolm Square

Table 07 shows the reasons for engaging in social recreational activities in Malcolm Square. Generally, the young millennials engage in social recreational activities in Malcolm Square for family reinforcement and bonding (42.8%), prestige (42.6%), and self-fulfillment (26.9%). These findings imply that the park is considered a pull factor for these reasons.

Table 07. Reasons for engaging in Social Recreational Activities in Malcolm Square

Activities	Frequency (F)	Percentage (%)
Self -fulfillment	29	26.9
Prestige	46	42.6
Romantic	5	4.8
Play	4	3.7
Family reinforcement and bonding	46	42.8
Social Interaction	37	34.3
Publicly Accessible	24	22.2
Educational Opportunity	26	24.1
Relaxation	6	5.6
Escape	11	10.2

Usual Behaviors in the Park Usage

Table 08. shows the distinct behavior of this demographic in the use of the park. Specifically, (84.3%) of the respondents just stand by, sit, and are idle, and (67.6%) use gadgets (play mobile games, take selfies and pictures, chat, etc.) This behavior connotes the manifestation of their spatial perception in Malcolm Square.

Table 08. Usual Behaviors in the Park Usage

Behavior	Frequency	Percentage
Standby/Sit and do nothing	91	84.3
Seeks attention	4	3.7
Forms a crowd	30	27.8
Desires ultimate control over the space	7	6.5
Becoming unhappy with limited choices of activities	18	16.7
Acts very impatiently, likes to move out	20	18.5
Uses gadgets (plays mobile games, takes selfies and pictures, chats, etc.)	73	67.6
Shows individualism and personal expression	46	42.6
Pursues new experiences	18	16.7

Designing and Retrofitting Malcolm Square

Table 9. showcases the design components primarily focusing on the park facilities and amenities. (45.5%) would want Malcolm Square to cater to covered walks, (38%) for promenade and sitting areas for prominent socializing and as a venue for entertainment purposes. Conversely, (14.8%) would want Malcolm Square to cultivate the cultural use aspect of the space as a mounting for cultural festivals and or exhibits.

Table 09. Designing and Retrofitting Malcolm Square
(Park Facilities to be Integrated in Malcolm Square)

Park Facilities /Amenities	Frequency	Percentage
Fountains/Drinking Fountain Areas	36	33.3
Covered Walks	49	45.5
Designated Areas/ walkways for PWDs	55	50.9
Designated Areas for Public Arts/Activities	34	31.5
Areas for Public Performance	15	13.9
Areas for mounting cultural festivals/exhibits	16	14.8
Promenade and sitting area for people-watching, discussions, and entertainment	41	38
Landscaping	78	72.2

Group Facilities to be integrated into the Design of Malcolm Square

Table 10. shows the group facilities needing to be integrated into the design aspects of Malcolm Square. These include a variety but notably (52.8%) suggest the addition of park benches and (51.9%) recommend Free Wi-Fi as a focal point in the design. Inversely (19.4%) of patrons recommend the goal of having security offices implemented in the design.

Table 10. Group Facilities to be integrated in the Design of Malcolm Square

Group Facilities	Frequency	Percentage
Jogging Track	13	12
Park Benches	57	52.8
Play Area	17	15.7
Free public toilet	43	39.8
Easy entry/exit	26	24.1
Security Offices	21	19.4
Free Wi-Fi	56	51.9
Gazebo	31	28.7
Solar Charging Areas	47	43.5
Tourist Assistance Booth	13	12

Photo documentation

Existing Conditions of Malcolm Square

Figure 07: BEHAVIOR SETTING

Figure 07. The existing features of Malcolm Square (A). This shows the existing sidewalks that surround Malcolm Square, there is a clear indication of its accessibility to other parts of the Central Business District because of this the center area of the park (B) serves as a transit zone where people utilize the space as transition points. Historical Buildings (D) are adjacent to the park namely Tiong San Bazaar, Teshmelitas (former U-Need), Abellera building, BPI Family Bank, Plaza Theatre building, and PS Bank building. These buildings were built during the American post-war period and were built more than fifty years thus they could be considered as potential buildings for historical significance, this will be considered for historical preservation. Parking spaces (C) are also located adjacent to the park, this affects the air quality of the place as well as the mobility of the pedestrians within the park.

Behavior Setting

ZONE A PERMANENT ZONE

(A) Main Entrance showing the Bust of Malcolm Square

(B) Location of Lighting Post / Trees and Planters

Group Facilities to be integrated into the Design of Malcolm Square

Table 10. shows the group facilities needing to be integrated into the design aspects of Malcolm Square. These include a variety but notably (52.8%) suggest the addition of park benches and (51.9%) recommend Free Wi-Fi as a focal point in the design. Inversely (19.4%) of patrons recommend the goal of having security offices implemented in the design.

ZONE B TEMPORARY ZONE

(D) Temporary Zone : Cultural Display/ Exhibits

The pictures are shown in Zone B; Temporary Zones or areas are intended to last for some time but not permanent. It connotes that these demographics can use the steps as seating areas to do this activity. It is perceived that the existing features of Malcolm Square contribute to the activities these demographics do

in the park. Further, the cultural exhibits seen in the picture indicate that Malcolm Square is still consistent with its actual use as a hub for cultural exhibits and public performances however, the behaviors of this demographic do not relate to the use of the park.

ZONE C: TRANSIT ZONES

Zone C: Transit Zone

The pictures above clearly indicate that the Park is also utilized as a transit zone to navigate to other areas within and outside the park. This connotes that the park also functions as a corridor leading to other parts of the Central Business District.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

Kevin Lynch's "Theory of Good City Forms" emphasizes the union of the quality of space and human activity characterized by identity, structure, congruence, and legibility. The existing features and conditions of Malcolm Square create an urban park that is convenient, safe, attractive, and vibrant. However, these features also became a venue for them to spend their time privately in public spaces. Studies show that

young millennials are motivated to visit Malcolm Square due to the "attractiveness of the place" and engage in social and recreational activities.

They define social recreation as activities that involve watching live events and concerts, public arts, public performances, and government services. It clearly shows that they are socially connected. The majority of these demographics visit Malcolm Square because it is publicly accessible however, they consider the park to be a convenient place to use cell phones, text, and social media. These findings signify that the park's intended use does not reconcile with its current use.

Spatial perception is the ability to be aware of our relationships with the environment around us. The young millennials' distinct behavior such as being idle, on standby, uses gadgets in the park indicates their association with technology and is strongly manifested in Malcolm Square. The activities of these demographics suggest the design to be integrated into Malcolm Square. The call for Urban Park retrofit is considered to attract more millennials to visit the park while creating a vibrancy that promotes socialization and strong community bonding.

Recommendation

Designing and Retrofitting Malcolm Square

The proposed Urban Park retrofit emanates from the young millennials' perception of space in Malcolm Square. It focused on the viability of making Malcolm Square fit for all generations while promoting sustainability and an environment-friendly environment within the Central Business District.

It is recommended that park and group facilities such as covered walks, landscaping, designated areas for the PWDs, additional park benches, free Wi-Fi zones, and solar charging areas could also promote in "drumming up" park visitors not only the young millennials but for everybody. It will be a catalyst for future park designs that will cater to all generations.

Landscapes and Vegetation

Trees contribute positively to the urban environment by providing green space screening. They also contribute to modifying urban micro-climate by their shading effect, cooling the air, reducing wind speed as well as intercepting rain at the same time providing an aesthetic enhancement to an arid and concreted environment while ameliorating noise and pollution.

Shades /Pergolas

Outdoor gardens feature forming a shaded walkway, passageway, or sitting area of vertical posts or pillars that usually support cross-beams and a sturdy open lattice, often upon which woody vines are trained.

Outdoor charging Stations with Maps and Billboards

Public charging areas will be provided with Maps and information about the city. This will be a useful facility since the majority of the pedestrians are cell phone users. The features of the PP&TC scheme which were valued highly by the social sectors in terms of convenience if facilities like mobile charging stations and tourist information centers were provided in the area.

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References

Galanakis, M. (2013). Intercultural Public Spaces in Multicultural Toronto. *Canadian Journal of Urban Research*, 22(1), 67–89. <https://doi.org/10.2307/26193926>

Hampton KN, Sessions L and Her EJ (2011c) Core networks, social isolation, and new media: Internet and mobile phone use, network size, and diversity. *Information, Communication & Society* 14: 130–155.

Hampton, K. N., Goulet, L. S., & Albanesius, G. (2015). Change in the social life of urban public spaces: The rise of mobile phones and women, and the decline of aloneness over 30 years. Source: *Urban Studies*, 52(8), 1489–1504. <https://doi.org/10.2307/26146067>

Hornick, S. (2015). 7 ways to make your Parks Millennial Friendly. National Recreation and Park Association. Retrieved from <https://www.nrpa.org/blog/7-ways-to-makeyour-parks-millennial-friendly/>

New Forum, (2018) Millennial expectations for an authentic sense of place. Steel Creek Development. Retrieved from <https://www.bizjournals.com/charlotte/news/2018/10/04/millennial-expectationsfor-an-authentic-sense-of.html>

Maiers,, M. (2017) Our Future in the Hands of the Millennials Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5799841/>

PPS (2018). Project for Public Spaces. Eleven Principles for creating great Community Places. Retrieved from: <https://www.pps.org/article/11steps>

Rebollo,P. (2018) A structural model of millennial tourist behavior towards tourism in Davao Region Retrieved from <https://tafpublications.com/platform/Articles/full-jahss4.1.3.php>

Sennett R (1977) *The Fall of Public Man*. New York: Knopf. Hampton KN, Livio O and Goulet LS (2010) The social life of wireless urban spaces: Internet use, social networks, and the public realm. *Journal of Communication* 60: 701–722.

Velasco, C (2019) Millennials in the university: An Inquiry on Burn-out among Filipino University Students.

Walker, A. (2016) Millennials Will Live in Cities, Unlike Anything We've Ever Seen Before. Retrieved from <https://gizmodo.com/millennials-will-live-in-cities-unlike-anythingweve-se-1716074100>

Worpole, K., & Knox, K. (n.d.). The social value of public spaces. Retrieved from <https://www.jrf.org.uk/sites/default/files/jrf/migrated/files/2050-public-spacecommunity.pdf>